

POLYESTER BASED NANOCOMPOSITE FIBRES: MORPHOLOGICAL AND MECHANICAL INVESTIGATIONS

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SUMMARY

Melt spun fibres based on poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) and multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) have been investigated. Evaluations performed by varying the nanotubes' content and their aspect ratio allowed to relate morphological observations with mechanical and dynamic-mechanical behaviour of nanostructured fibres.

Keywords: Poly(butylene terephthalate), nanocomposite, carbon nanotubes, fibres

INTRODUCTION

Poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) is a semicrystalline polymer widely used in many industrial fields thanks to its excellent processability and good resistance to a broad range of chemicals [1-2]. However, the continuous need to extend and develop new commercial applications have dealt the research to further improve its performances by inclusion of opportune fillers [3-8]. In this context, recently the interest has been strongly devoted to additives having at least one dimension on the nanometer scale [9-11] to obtain new nanostructured materials. As well established, nanosized additives offer extraordinary advantages over traditional reinforcements since their high aspect ratio and associated high surface area to volume ration to allow the achievement of specific targets even at relatively very low contents. Among these additives, carbon nanotubes, since their discovery, in the early nineties, have shown an ever increasing interest owing to their intrinsic outstanding properties combined with their usually high aspect ratio [12-14]. However, it has been also demonstrated that the achievement of products with appealing performances requires good dispersion of nanofillers as well as an efficient load transfer with the hosting matrix. Thus, since the existence of intermolecular van der Waals interactions between nanotubes, normally resulting in the formation of aggregates, simultaneous efforts have been spent also to reduce these phenomena in nanotube based composites [15-17].

The preparation of nanostructured materials is usually carried out by using various technologies such as in-situ polymerization [18,19], solution compounding [20,21], sol-gel [22,23], melt compounding [24-26] even if the last one is well recognised as the most promising approach mainly owing to its low cost, high productivity and compatibility with typical processing techniques.

In light of the above considerations, main objective of this research was to assess the influence of content and aspect ratio of commercial multi wall carbon nanotubes on mechanical and dynamic mechanical properties of melt spun poly(butylene terephthalate) based fibres and to verify how these experimental results are related with morphological features highlighting, among others, the actual level of nanotube dispersion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) used in this study as the hosting matrix was supplied by Lanxess GmbH under the trade name POCAN B 1505. MFI= 20g/10 min.

Multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) were purchased from Shenzhen Nanotechport Co. Ltd, China. These latter have diameters in the range 10-30, 20-40, 40-60 and 60-100 nm, a length of 5-15 μm , surface area equal to 40-300 m^2/g and a purity >95%.

Preparation of nanocomposite fibres

All materials were dried using a vacuum oven at 80 °C over night before processing to minimize the effects of moisture. The PBT/MWNTs nanocomposites were prepared in a HAAKE counter-rotating twin screw-extruder by setting the extrusion zone temperature from 200 to 240°C and the screw speed at 90 rpm. Nanotube contents equal to 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0 wt% were considered. Systematic thermogravimetric measurements discussed elsewhere always confirmed a fair correlation between nominal and actual filler contents.

Extrudates, pelletized with a Haake pelletizer, were re-dried under the same protocol cited above and then melt spun by a DSM spinning line to obtain fibres having a diameter approximately equal to 180 μmeters .

Characterization techniques

Morphological observations on 110-120 nm-thick microtomed sections derived from samples previously embedded in an epoxy resin were performed by using a Transmission Electron Microscope Philips EM 208 equipped with a high definition data acquisition system Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions.

Tensile tests were run at room conditions by employing an Instron Machine (Model 4301). The testing conditions were a grip distance of 15 mm, a load cell of 1 kN and a cross-head speed of 36 mm/min. Each specimen was prepared gluing single fibre ends onto a paper frame according to the procedure described in ASTM D3379. For each material at least ten specimens were tested and characteristic parameters, at low and high applied deformations, were averaged to obtain mean values.

Dynamic mechanical measurements were done by using a DMA Tritec 2000 from Triton Technology Ltd. in tensile mode at a constant frequency of 1Hz and over a range of temperatures from -40°C to 150°C. For each sample, heated at a rate of 2°/min,

variation of viscoelastic parameters such as: storage modulus (E') and mechanical loss factor ($\tan \delta = E''/E'$) were recorded as a function of temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrographs of ultramicrotomed sections have been obtained for all sample in both longitudinal and transverse direction. As indicated by photos of samples containing nanotubes with different diameters and compared in figure 1, MWNTs appear to be dispersed homogeneously within the polymer matrix although some aggregates are formed, as expected.

Figure 1. TEM micrographs (5600 x – marker=2000 nm) obtained in longitudinal direction of composite fibre containing MWNT 1030 (a), 2040 (b), 4060 (c) and 60100 (d)

Tensile properties

Mechanical parameters such as Young's modulus, tensile strength and deformation at break, derived from typical stress strain curves, are collected in tables 1 and 2. In particular, Table 1 summarizes data obtained by varying MWNTs content examining additions of the smallest and the highest available diameter, respectively, while, in Table 2, the effect of nanotube diameters (aspect ratio) at a fixed nanotube content (0.5 wt%) is highlighted.

Table 1. Effect of MWNTs content on mechanical parameters of composite fibres with respect to neat PBT ones

MWNTs content (wt%)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
Neat PBT	2427	62	662
MWNT 1030			
0.2	2459	69	1127
0.5	2525	65	1300
1	2802	74	991
MWNT 60100			
0.2	2594	62	937
0.5	2731	74	1040
1	2637	67	866

Table 2. Effect of MWNTs diameter at a fixed concentration on mechanical parameters of composite fibres with respect to neat PBT ones

MWNTs diameter (nm)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
Neat PBT	2427	62	662
0.5 wt% MWNT			
10-30	2525	61	1300
20-40	2968	68	1186
40-60	2858	65	1075
60-100	2731	74	1040

In details, the inclusion of nanotubes always involves a preliminary increase of the Young modulus at least up to a critical content, the amount of which seems to be related to the MWNTs diameter or, in other words, to the nanotubes' aspect ratio. The modulus improvement is usually accompanied by an increase of both tensile strength and ultimate deformation with respect to the values shown by neat polyester fibre.

The improvement of the stiffness of composite fibres could be partly ascribed to the well known nucleating effect of the included filler that slightly modify the crystallinity in terms of extent and/or size distribution giving rise to an increase of the crystallization temperature (T_c), as generally confirmed by thermal and structural investigations [27,28]. On the other hand, eventual interactions at the interphase, which is currently being investigated, could constrain adjacent amorphous areas, having extension increasing with the aspect ratio of dispersed nanofillers, further stiffening the hosting matrix.

Analogous considerations may be drawn in terms of fibres tensile strength while, regarding the elongation at break, a marked increase of deformability in drawing process is always recorded for composite fibres with respect to neat polyester ones. However, also for this tensile parameter, a non monotonic trend is revealed with a reversal behaviour for filler contents normally exceeding 0.5 wt%: effect usually explainable in terms of an increased clustering tendency.

As far as carbon nanotubes diameter is concerned, non strictly monotonic trends are revealed for both Young modulus and tensile strength of fibres while a continuous decrease of the elongation at break characterizing the PBT based fibres has been shown (see Table 2).

Dynamic mechanical properties

The storage modulus and the loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of composite fibres are compared to the reference PBT ones, processed under the same conditions, in figures 2 and 3, respectively. In particular effects of addition of nanotubes having the smallest and the highest available diameter on these two viscoelastic parameters have been analysed.

Clearly, in all nano composite fibres, the incorporation of nanotubes with the highest aspect ratio (1030) causes increases of the stiffness all over the investigated range of temperature except in the glass transition region. This positive trend, as already demonstrated for tensile properties, is variable with the content of the reinforcing filler and may be explained mainly assuming the occurrence of phenomena usually revealed in similar nanostructured formulations such as the organization of this latter in networks able to increase the stiffness/consistency of the amorphous phase in its glassy/rubbery state.

For fibres including MWNTs 60100, instead, benefits for glassy and rubbery regions appear to be verified only for the content equal to 0.2 wt%. Further additions of nanotubes involve negligible improvements of the rubbery storage modulus but even a worsening of the glassy one. These detrimental effects could be related to the formation of MWNT aggregates showing not negligible sizes.

Regarding the loss factor, inclusion of carbon nanotubes, besides their aspect ratio, involve a decrease of the peak height. This behaviour could still be explained assuming

the existence of interactions between MWNTs and polyester matrix to reduce the mechanical damping ability of the amorphous phase.

Figure 2. Storage modulus (E') of neat PBT and PBT based nanocomposite fibres containing 0.2, 0.5, 1.0 wt% of MWNTs 1030 (a) and MWNTs 60100 (b)

Figure 3. Loss factor (Tan δ) of neat PBT and PBT based nanocomposite fibres containing 0.2, 0.5, 1.0 wt% of MWNTs 1030 (a) and MWNTs 60100 (b)

Finally, the same viscoelastic parameters have been compared by taking constant the nanotubes content (0,5 wt%) but varying their diameter in order to emphasize effects mainly due to aspect ratio of included nanofillers (see figures 4 a and b).

At this regard, it is reasonable to assume that, in the process, the greater the diameter of the nanotubes, the more likely are interactions among nanotubes with respect to ones between nanotubes and hosting matrix. These phenomena, Promoting the formation of aggregates as well as of network structures dispersed in the matrix amorphous phase, could justify the significant increase of the storage modulus, for both glassy and rubbery regions, of composite fibres containing the largest nanotubes (MWNTs 60100) with respect to neat polyester fibres and appear to be responsible of reductions of the relative mechanical damping especially in presence of fillers having the highest aspect ratio (MWNTs 1030), in correspondence of which foreseen interactions would be maximised.

CONCLUSIONS

Melt spun polyester nanocomposite fibre based on poly(butylene terephthalate) and low amounts of multiwall carbon nanotubes, having the same average length but different diameter distributions, have been examined in terms of morphological characteristics and mechanical properties evaluated in quasi-static and dynamic ways.

The used process conditions appeared to ensure a relatively uniform dispersion of nanotubes and a growing tendency towards the formation of dispersed aggregates and networks by increasing content and size of the same. This structural organizations, lowering the so-called percolation threshold, contribute to support amorphous phase even at temperatures higher than the glass transition region, increase the ductility at room conditions but reduce damping performances of the nanocomposite.

In conclusion, besides further benefits that could be expected by increasing the draw ratio and, thus, the alignment of rod-like fillers, the research confirmed strong relationships among amount/aspect ratio of the dispersed additive and potentiality of nanostructured items based on.

Figure 4. (a) Storage modulus (E') and (b) loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of neat PBT and PBT based nanocomposite fibres at a fixed content (0.5 wt%) of MWNTs

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